

D6.2

**Release of complete set of
communication materials and tools,
incl. the public website V 1.0**

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D6.2 Release of complete set of communication materials and tools, incl. the public website V 1.0

Deliverable lead beneficiary: AI

Authors: Sophie Rau

Internal Technical Auditor	Name (Beneficiary short name)	Date of approval
Task leader	Sophie Rau (AI)	11.05.2022
WP leader	Sophie Rau (AI)	11.05.2022
Coordinator	Carl-Friedrich Schleussner (HU)	13.05.2022
Project Office	Sophie Rau (AI)	17.05.2022

Abstract: This report describes the complete set of communication materials and tools, including the public website (V 1.0). The tools will support the communication activities to raise the awareness in the general public, to reach out beyond the main stakeholder groups of the project and widely distribute project results to different target audiences.

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Glossary

ABBREVIATION / ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Climate Analytics
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IR	Iconic Regions
PPO	PROVIDE Project Office
RWD	Responsive Web Design
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

This document describes the release of all communication materials and tools, which will be used to support the communication activities of PROVIDE and widely distribute project results to different target audiences. The main communication tool is the project website. An overview of the design, structure and contents of the public website set up for PROVIDE as part of the project dissemination strategy is provided in this report.

The website is accessible under the URL <https://www.provide-h2020.eu/> and maintained by the PROVIDE Project Office (PPO). It is based on responsive web design (RWD), which provides an optimal viewing and interaction experience – easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling – across a wide range of devices from desktop computer monitors to mobile phones and tablets. The website development team consists of a designer, a web developer, an editor, and content specialists, who worked collaboratively together.

Another important communication tool is the PROVIDE twitter channel (@PROVIDE4CLIMATE) to increase public awareness and reach out to stakeholders. Further communication tools, such as newsletter and a you tube channel will be released during the project duration.

2. PROVIDE visual identity

A project visual identity has been developed by a professional designer at project start. The objective of the PROVIDE visual identity is to provide the project with a recognisable and coherent image by visible elements, such as typography, pictures and layout. The design reflects a consistent look and feel. All communication and dissemination tools of PROVIDE (social media accounts, website, newsletter etc.) using a coherent design. The PROVIDE visual identity contains a project logo, fonts and colours and is used for all internal and external communication tools, such as templates, the public website, social media channels, newsletter etc.

2.1. Logo

The project logo (Figure 1) reveals the PROVIDE identity and distinguishes PROVIDE from other projects, so that it can be easily recognized and associated with the project values. It reflects the innovative approach of the project and its tasks. As the PROVIDE project aims to deliver information on overshoot scenarios and respective impacts in the context of adaptation through an innovative web tool (PROVIDE Dashboard), the logo symbolizes an overshoot curve and the colour gradient of the „I“ is associated with the „burning embers“ effect of the IPCC. The colour scheme of the logo is captured in the website design. The logo is used in all PROVIDE documentations, publications and communication material.

Figure 1: PROVIDE logo

3. Public Website

3.1. Objectives

The public PROVIDE website can be reached at <https://www.provide-h2020.eu>; a domain, which is simple to remember. As part of the project communication and dissemination activities the main objective of the website is to ensure that the impact of the project and its results will be achieved at societal and political levels. Besides other dissemination and communication tools (e.g., social media, general communication material such as flyers etc.), the website guarantees that EU-funded research is adequately communicated to all relevant stakeholders and target audiences. The website promotes the main benefits resulting from the project and depicts the necessity to further develop innovative climate services, taking the impacts of overshoot scenarios into account.

The 1.5°C Paris Agreement temperature goal provides the benchmark for global climate action to avoid the most devastating impacts of climate change. However, under current trajectories, overshooting (meaning the temporary exceedance of 1.5°C) the Paris temperature thresholds is a distinct possibility. The impacts of such overshoot scenarios would be particularly consequential for vulnerable regions and systems. Here, even in the case of only a temporary exceedance of 1.5°C, thresholds of abrupt and possibly

irreversible shifts or adaptation limits may be exceeded. The PROVIDE project aims to deliver information on overshoot scenarios and respective impacts in the context of adaptation through an innovative web tool (PROVIDE Climate Services Dashboard). You will be able to assess the risks of overshooting systemic thresholds (e.g., glacier melt) from the local to the global level. Moving beyond a limited set of climate scenarios, the PROVIDE approach allows you to make thresholds the starting point for the analysis and adaptation planning.

The PROVIDE Climate Services Dashboard (linked to the project website) will be an online platform providing detailed information on overshoot scenarios and expected impacts and their reversibility, with unique sectoral coverage including extreme events, biodiversity, cryosphere, sea level rise, agriculture, economic damages, socio-economic vulnerabilities among others.

The innovative approach of PROVIDE – the development of a Climate Service Dashboard – is explained for the public at large on the website. As soon as a first version of the Dashboard will be online, a direct link will be included on the homepage of the website.

The main target group for the website is relevant stakeholders. A dedicated subpage is describing the stakeholder co-development process and enables interested, new stakeholders to sign-up to get involved.

Furthermore, the website presents the scientific idea, promotes expected impact of the project and the project structure is outlined. The website will also be a portal to disseminate PROVIDE scientific publications, tools/data and to present the main activities and next steps to be taken. It contains information about the consortium, with detailed descriptions of the partners involved and the Coordinator and the PROVIDE Project Office as contact points.

To establish a channel of communication between research, stakeholders and public, the website development focused on a user-friendly and unique design, effective navigation, browser consistency, fast loading pages and mobile compatibility. The objective is to present the complex content clearly structured, considering SEO factors (keywords in headings, first sentences and paragraphs). As the website will be updated frequently in order to provide the latest publications and news, a state-of-the-art content management system has been chosen, which is easy to use, so that the content can be changed quickly according to the projects progress.

3.2. Target audience

The PROVIDE public website targets a wide range of audiences, such as:

- Stakeholders (Regional/local and EU)
 - Policy makers (Regional/local and EU policy level)
 - The scientific community
 - Climate service providers
 - International organisations and foundations
 - Local/regional and international NGOs
 - Sensitive business sectors
 - Climate Litigation representatives
- The general public
- Funding authorities, including the EC
- Press representatives/journalists

However, the main target group are relevant stakeholder, especially from the iconic regions (IR), as subpages for each IR will be developed and interested stakeholders can [sign up](#) to get involved via the website.

3.3. Design

Considering current website design trends and user behaviour, the design is clear and minimalist. This enables an intuitive and easy navigation following the fact that users are rather browsing websites than reading long articles. The distinctive design facilitates to communicate the PROVIDE objectives, the benefits of the concept and values of the PROVIDE research. Therefore, the design reflects a consistent look and feel within the subpages of the website, but also beyond. All communication and dissemination tools of PROVIDE (social media accounts, flyer ect.) use a coherent design. The topography is well chosen, also considering to be user-friendly, and corresponds with the logo. The PROVIDE website features captivating banners and catchy slogans (e.g. “Paris Agreement Overshooting”; „Innovative Climate Services“), which are easy to remember and take into account SEO factors. High quality photographs contribute to a strong visual identity and support the communication of the key message. The banner is presented as a slideshow and each menu button is represented by an own picture.

3.4. Technical Implementation

The website is programmed in responsive web design (RWD). RWD is an approach to web design aimed at crafting sites to provide an optimal viewing and interaction experience – easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling – across a wide range of devices from desktop computer monitors to mobile phones. The technical challenges include to program fast loading pages, to ensure browser consistency and to optimize for high search engine rankings. The mobile design has been implemented with a so-called hamburger menu. Interactive elements have been minimized in order to facilitate fast loading pages.

3.5. Structure and content

A good and simple site structure helps the user as well as search engines to navigate the site. The PROVIDE website is characterized by a minimalist header, just including the logo and the horizontal menu bar, a body and a large footer. The EU emblem is displayed in the footer as well as a disclaimer stating that the PROVIDE project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. With this, the requirement to promote the action and visibility of funding as set out in Articles 27.3, 28.2, 29.4 and 38.1.2 of the H2020 General Model Grant Agreement is fulfilled. Furthermore, the footer includes the PROVIDE logo, linked social media icon (Twitter) and Imprint/Privacy Policy/Copyright. The header and footer are consistent on all pages of the PROVIDE website.

The menu bar displays the main pages of the website: *Home – About – Stakeholder – Tools and Data – News – Innovation Place*. The subpages can be reached via buttons on the main pages (such as Work Packages under *About*).

3.5.1. Home

Paris Agreement Overshooting – Reversibility, Climate Impacts and Adaptation Needs:
The homepage is the first impression of the website, and the visual identity influences the further engagement of the visitor (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Homepage (1)

To catch the visitor's attention, a slide show with catchy slogans and pictures are displayed. A short text features the Climate Service Dashboard and project summary.

In the centre of the homepage the buttons are placed: *Get involved* (link to the stakeholder page to sign-up as a stakeholder) – *Newsletter* (to sign-up for the Newsletter) – *Contact* (to contact the CO via email) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Homepage – contact (2)

The latest news from the *News* page are also displayed on the homepage (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Homepage – news (3)

3.5.2. About

The *About* page combines the main information about the PROVIDE project, including information about the consortium and the Work Packages (Figure 5 – Figure 7).

Figure 5: About page (1)

Figure 6: About page - Consortium (2)

WP1 FUNDAMENTALS OF OVERSHOOT PATHWAYS

Lead Partner: Imperial College London

WP2 BIOPHYSICAL IMPACTS

Lead Partner: ETH Zürich

WP3 OVERSHOOT PROOFING FOR ENHANCED ADAPTATION DECISION MAKING AND POLICY

Lead Partner: Universität Hamburg

Figure 7: About page - WPs (3)

3.5.3. Stakeholder

The Stakeholder co-development process is one of the most important feature of PROVIDE (Figure 8). Interested stakeholders can directly sign-up a questionnaire to get involved. It's planned that each IR will have its own subpage (Figure 9), which will present the results of the IR Engagement meetings.

Up to date Climate Services focusing on threshold exceeding risks

Are you looking for reliable, up to date climate impact information for your region? Do you need high resolution modelling for your city? Are you interested in the impacts of overshoot scenarios and would you like to overshoot proof your adaptation measures?

Then you should join our group of global and regional stakeholders. We provide impact information for policy relevant scenarios on global, national, regional and city level. Furthermore, we will co-develop an interactive

webtool (the PROVIDE Climate Services Dashboard) together with you to provide impact information, and to explore scenarios that do not exceed certain thresholds. The Climate Service Dashboard will be available open access to all stakeholders, who are responsible for planning, using and/or improving overshoot adaptation capacities.

A first set of regional workshops in the Iconic Regions was conducted in March/April 2022, where input on the

concept of the Climate Services Dashboard was gathered. On European level, we are looking for stakeholders to join us in overshoot proofing two EU adaptation strategies. Webinars and workshops are planned to start in late 2022 or early 2023. If you are interested in becoming a stakeholder, please share your information here.

Figure 8: Stakeholder page (1)

4 ICONIC REGIONS AND CITIES

PROVIDE addresses regional and sub-regional (city level) adaptation requirements for iconic regions (IR) including a focus on climate change and extreme weather events. These are places where greater climate risks are expected to occur, and where the impact of climate change is likely to be most significant. The IRs are defined based on the impact of climate change and the potential for adaptation. The IRs are defined based on the impact of climate change and the potential for adaptation.

IR1: ARCTIC FENNOSCANDIA

City of choice: Helsinki

ARctic cities within a coastal setting, development of cities at risk, along with increasing frequency of extreme events in the Arctic. Adaptation to an increasing number of extreme events and the potential for adaptation. The IR is defined based on the impact of climate change and the potential for adaptation.

IR2: IBERIAN MEDITERRANEAN

Location: Mediterranean, Africa, Portugal

The Iberian Mediterranean is a coastal and sub-coastal region, defined by the impact of climate change and the potential for adaptation.

Figure 9: Stakeholder page (2)

3.5.4. Tools & Data

The *Tools & Data* page will be continuously updated, and the latest tools will be included (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Tools & Data page

3.5.5. News

The *News* page (Figure 11) features the latest project news, organised in different categories.

Figure 11: News Page

3.5.6. Innovation Place

This page is linked to the Innovation Place website. An Open Innovation platform supporting collaborative research through the matching of pre-screened R&D projects, qualified organisations, and public funding opportunities. PROVIDE partners can directly login the internal project workspace (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Innovation Place Page

4. Social Media

In addition to the public website, PROVIDE has a strong presence on the social media platform Twitter. Latest news, achievements, milestones and events from PROVIDE will be promoted, linking to the main website for more information. The PROVIDE Twitter channel provides the opportunity for the public to engage with the PROVIDE project. Twitter is mainly used for networking with key stakeholders as well as the general public, journalists and the scientific community.

5. Newsletter

A newsletter template has been designed. Subscription to the Newsletter is possible via the project website. The newsletter will summarise the relevant achievements and results of the project, as they become available. The newsletters will be also issued to announce and introduce the Overshoot Adaptation Webinars and will therefore focus on the specific topic covered by each webinar. They will be distributed towards the PROVIDE Stakeholder Community, the Twitter channel and partners communication departments.

6. General Communication material (poster, flyer)

PROVIDE partner CA has produced a general project flyer (Figure 13) at project start for interested stakeholder and to promote PROVIDE project. As the visual project identity has been set up, the project flyer will be updated soon to reflect the new PROVIDE design. It will be uploaded on the project website. During the project duration, if physical meetings will take place, posters might be produced as well. This communication material will be distributed at workshops, conferences, events and, if needed, will be updated over the project lifetime.

PROVIDE Paris Agreement Overshooting
Reversibility, Climate Impacts and Adaptation Needs

PROJECT SUMMARY
The 1.5°C Paris Agreement temperature goal provides the benchmark for global climate action to avoid the most devastating impacts of climate change. However, under current trajectories, overshooting (meaning the temporary exceedance of 1.5°C) the Paris temperature threshold is a distinct possibility. The impacts of such overshoot scenarios would be particularly consequential for vulnerable regions and systems. Here, even in the case of only a temporary exceedance of 1.5°C, thresholds of abrupt and possibly irreversible shifts or adaptation limits may be exceeded.

The PROVIDE project aims to deliver information on overshoot scenarios and respective impacts in the context of adaptation through an interactive web tool. You will be able to assess the risks of overshooting systemic thresholds (e.g. glacier melt) from the local to the global level. Moving beyond a limited set of climate scenarios, the PROVIDE approach allows you to make thresholds the starting point for the analysis and adaptation planning.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- Produce global multi-scenario, multi-sectoral climate information
- Assess climate system uncertainties and feedbacks
- Co-develop a generalisable Overshoot Proofing Methodology
- Identify and prioritise adaptation needs in 4 Iconic Regions
- Integrate all project outcomes into a Climate Service Dashboard

The PROVIDE Climate Service Dashboard will be an online platform providing detailed information on overshoot scenarios and expected impacts and their reversibility, with unique sectoral coverage including extreme events, biodiversity, cryosphere, sea level rise, agriculture, economic damages, socio-economic vulnerabilities among others. The information includes global, national and city level modelling results. The design and the presentation of the data will be co-developed together with stakeholders.

Finally an overshoot proofing module for adaptation planning will be made available for adaptation planners. The Overshoot Proofing Methodology will be developed together with stakeholders within the PROVIDE project.

THE SCIENTIFIC IDEA

Within the PROVIDE project we want to reverse the impact chain to allow e.g. adaptation specialists to set risk thresholds for societal impacts (e.g. health issues due to heatwaves) or geographical impacts (e.g. sea level rise) so that they can analyse under which conditions these impacts can be avoided. The analysis will be based on a multi-scenario framework for overshoot pathways and a cross-scale chain of computationally light-weight emulators, linking global emission pathways to regional sectoral impacts and urban climate risk projections.

Furthermore, PROVIDE will assess risks of high-end global warming for sectoral impacts and potential irreversible impacts of overshoots including for sea level rise, permafrost loss, glacier loss and terrestrial and marine species.

STAKEHOLDER CO-DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

One ambition of PROVIDE is to co-develop the PROVIDE Climate Service Dashboard together with practitioners, scientists, litigation experts, business, civil society and all other potential users interested in the PROVIDE approach. We want to advance collaboration between potential users of climate impact information, researchers and providers of climate services to develop stakeholder-oriented climate science and community engaged overshoot issues in adaptation planning. It is our intention to increase the ownership and openness of decision makers and regional urban planners to customise and use the PROVIDE tools (e.g. the Climate Service dashboard) and methods for their specific adaptation planning.

If you are interested to engage please [register here](#) or read more on our website: www.provide-h2020.eu

*Overshoot scenarios: Pathways that exceed the stabilisation level (concentration, forcing or temperature) before the end of the time horizon of interest (e.g. before 2100) and then decline towards that level by that time. Once the target level is re-achieved, removal by sinks of greenhouse gases is required. (Source: IPCC Glossary)

© PROVIDE consortium in collaboration of leading research institutes and all details and responsibilities, who benefit and adaptation reports who directly or indirectly contribute to the study, to support facilitate contribution to development process with wider array of stakeholders.

PROVIDE INTEGRATED MODELLING APPROACH FOR ADAPTATION PLANNING ACROSS SCALES

OVERSHOOT TOPOLOGY and business STORYLINES of various regions and adaptation needs

GLOBAL TO REGIONAL Climate projections

REGIONAL AND URBAN IMPACTS AND ADAPTATION

SECTORAL CLIMATE IMPACT PROJECTIONS involving

CLIMATE SERVICE DASHBOARD

4 ICONIC REGIONS AND CITIES

PROVIDE has four Iconic Regions (IR) which will serve as case study regions where more detailed information will be made available and close collaboration with local and regional stakeholders is planned.

PROVIDE will assess regional and local impacts of overshoot pathways and required adaptation responses in the four IR, including a focus on selected urban environments within those regions.

These are places where physical risks overlay with specific socio-economic vulnerabilities and were selected to serve as Iconic Case (IC) where the PROVIDE Overshoot Proofing Methodology will be co-developed. They will provide entry points for raising awareness about the need for enhanced adaptation action under overshoot scenarios and offer a practical tested for generalisable urban planning approaches.

IR1: Arctic Fennoscandia - City of Bodø, Norway
IR2: Iberian Mediterranean - Lisbon Metropolitan Area, Portugal
IR3: Indian Basin - City of Islamabad, Pakistan
IR4: Caribbean Small Islands - City of Nassau, The Bahamas

PRACTICAL RELEVANCE

- Exploring global, EU and regional risks and impacts of climate change under current NDC pathways vs Paris Agreement limits and overshoot implications
- Overshoot proofing reports for two EU sectoral adaptation strategies (agriculture and infrastructure)
- Online overshoot proofing module supplementing existing adaptation decision-proofing tools and applicable to EU, national and local adaptation policies and related decision-making frameworks
- High-resolution modelling for 100 cities globally including 40 cities in Europe

SECTORAL CLIMATE IMPACT PROJECTIONS

Investigating the (ir)reversibility of impacts under overshoot pathways on a regional scale.

- Extreme weather events
- Carbon cycle, biodiversity, wildfires and species loss
- Cryosphere loss, sea level rise and oceanic impacts
- Agriculture, economic damages and socio-economic vulnerability

Figure 13: Preliminary Flyer (Design will be updated)

7. Internal communication material

7.1. Templates

Together with the logo, templates for presentations and other documentation have been developed (Figure 14 – Figure 16). The PROVIDE Microsoft PowerPoint (PPT) templates are coherent with the PROVIDE visual identity, including the fonts. The design of the cover slide is taken up the lines of the logo. The templates are being regularly used by the project partners for internal and external presentations.

Figure 14: PPT Template - cover slide (1)

Simple layout

- Chapter 1
- Chapter 2
- Chapter 3
- Chapter 4
- Chapter 5
- Chapter 6
- Chapter 7

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Figure 15: PPT Template - content slide (2)

Figure 16: PPT Template - chapter cover slide (3)

The PROVIDE Microsoft Word Templates that are used for all text documents, e.g., deliverables, meeting agenda and minutes. For EC deliverables a specific cover and template had been designed (see the cover of this report).

8. Conclusion

The PROVIDE public website is online and fully operational since 10 March 2022 and is running smoothly. Browser consistency and the mobile interface had been continuously improved throughout the development process. The page will be updated and maintained on a frequent basis, editorially and technically. Updates will become more and more frequent as the project progresses. The website will be an important means to communicate and disseminate information about the project and to attract all relevant stakeholders.